

Metal Complexes of N-Acetylacetone-aurine Schiff base

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THE results of physico-chemical studies on the solid complexes of N-Acetylacetone-aurine (H_2AT) with some bivalent metal ions are reported in this communication.

Taurine supplied by Fluka was used without further purification. Acetylacetone BDH (L.R.) was redistilled before use. All other compounds were of BDH grade. Elemental analyses, molecular weights, magnetic susceptibility and electronic absorption spectra were determined by standard methods as already reported¹.

Preparation of H_2AT and its metal complexes: H_2AT was prepared by the method of Pfeiffer *et al.*². Its metal complexes with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and $UO_2(II)$ were synthesised by the method of Yamada *et al.*^{3,4} The pyridine adducts of the metal complexes were obtained by the method reported earlier¹.

Analysis: Found: C, 40.34; H, 6.19; N, 6.62; S, 15.31; Calcd. for $C_7H_{13}NSO_4$: C, 40.57; H, 6.28; N, 6.76; S, 15.45%, m.p. 141°.

Results and Discussions

Elemental analyses, molecular weights, magnetic and spectral data of the hydrated complexes are given in Table I.

Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes correspond to the composition $[MLX_3]$ where M = metal ion, X = H_2O or Py and $LH_2 = (C_7H_{13}NSO_4)$. The magnetic moments obtained reveal the presence of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electron in the Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes, respectively. The little lower values of the magnetic moment of Mn(II)-complex (Table I) may be due to spin-exchange in its solid state or to the presence of little Mn(III) species which may have been caused due to aerial oxidation as reported earlier⁵ for such complexes. The high magnetic moment of Co(II)-complex appears to be due to spin-orbit coupling. The electronic absorption spectra of Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes in dioxane and pyridine indicate that the frequencies correspond to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(D)$ for the Mn(II) complex, ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g(D)$ for the Fe(II)-complex, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ for the Co(II)-complex, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ for Ni(II)-complex and ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ for the Cu(II)-complex. These data supported by their magnetic moments confirm near octahedral structure for Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II)-complexes and a tetragonal configuration for the Cu(II)-complex. The tetragonal structure of Cu(II)-complex is also apparent from Jahn-Teller effect⁶. Infrared analysis of the metal complexes in the region 3.1-4.0 μ confirms in them the presence of coordinated water molecules.

TABLE I—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS, ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF N-ACETYLACETONE-TAURINE

Metal complex	Mol. Wt.	Metal %	N %	H_2O %	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 298°K	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹ Dioxane/Pyridine
$[Mn(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X_3]$	307(313.93)	17.42(17.49)	4.36(4.45)	17.11(17.20)	5.82	24750/23900 29800/28950
$[Fe(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X_3]$	308(314.87)	17.63(17.74)	4.38(4.44)	17.00(17.14)	5.49	10800/11100
$[Co(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X_3]$	319(317.93)	18.48(18.53)	4.29(4.403)	16.72(16.98)	5.18	17500/18000 21200/21500
$[Ni(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X_3]$	310(317.71)	18.40(18.47)	4.29(4.406)	16.79(16.99)	3.10	13800/13200 23600/23000
$[Cu(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X_3]$	318(322.54)	19.54(19.69)	4.30(4.34)	16.63(16.74)	1.90	13900/12850
$[Pd(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X]$	321(329.4)	32.17(32.30)	4.11(4.25)	5.32(5.46)	—	22400/22000 26300/25900 30400/30100
$[Zn(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X]$	280(288.37)	22.51(22.66)	4.68(4.85)	6.10(6.24)	—	—
$[Cd(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X]$	325(335.4)	33.39(33.53)	4.05(4.16)	5.21(5.36)	—	—
$[UO_2(C_7H_{11}NSO_4)_3X]$	480(493.0)	54.58(54.76)	2.71(2.83)	3.54(3.65)	—	—

Calculated values are given in parenthesis. X refers to water. Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) and $UO_2(II)$ -complexes were found to be diamagnetic, as expected.

The Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -complexes also display 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry besides having a water or pyridine molecule. All these compounds were found to be diamagnetic. Based on these data a tetrahedral structure is assigned to Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes and an octahedral structure to $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -complex.

The Pd(II) complex indicates three absorption bands with their peaks at 22400, 26300 and 30400 cm^{-1} assignable to the transitions, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$. Thus the Pd(II) complex displays a squareplanar configuration. These results are also in agreement with an earlier finding⁷.

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Modified Synthesis of Tris(Biguanide) Cobalt (III) Base and its Salts

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THE title compounds have been the subject of many investigations : asymmetric transformation of the second order during resolution¹, intramolecular twist mechanism of racemisation², inner sphere formation constant³, aquation kinetics⁴, outer sphere association constants⁵, filter paper and thin layer chromatography⁶. Original synthesis⁷ involved an over-cautious, somewhat cumbersome and lengthy air

oxidation of the insoluble bis(biguanide) cobalt(II) base in presence of alkaline biguanide. We have been successfully using for many years now a quicker H_2O_2 oxidation procedure. A recent report by Krishnamurthy⁸ describing the efficacy of H_2O_2 in radically reducing the time of synthesis of trans- $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2] = \text{Cl}(\text{en} = \text{ethylenediamine})$ prompts us to describe our own on $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{OH})_3$ and its salts.

Biguanide acid sulfate⁹ (8.5 g) was dissolved in water (75 ml) containing NaOH (6.0 g). To this was added with stirring a solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.5 g) in water (5.0 ml) H_2O_2 (5.0 ml, 20 vol.) was added and the mixture heated on a steam bath for 30 min with stirring. The solution along with the red crystals of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{OH})_3$ were cooled in ice for 1 hr, filtered and the crystals washed with ice cold ethanol (25 ml.). The base was then triturated with ice cold HCl (1 : 3) to a pH $\sim$ 6.0. The orange red coloured tris(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride was filtered with the aid of ethanol (10 ml) and was finally recrystallised from hot water (70 ml.). Yield 2.6 g. Found : Cl, 22.74; Co, 12.80; Eq.wt. 156. Calcd.: Cl, 22.88; Co, 12.68; Eq.wt. 156.

The compound gave the two usual transitions ; $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ 21.1 kK; $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ 28.4 kK.

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Estimation of Ba^{2+} , Ag^+ and Tl^+ as chromates by A.C. Amperometry

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KOLTHOFF and Gregor^{1,2} estimated barium with chromate ion in aqueous and aqueous-ethanol mixtures by conventional amperometric titration which yielded results that were 2 to 5% low. Many

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